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Smart Cities Robot Competitions (SciRoc)
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ERL Professional

European Robotic League for Professional Service Robots

ERL Professional Rulebook

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**Hochschule
Bonn-Rhein-Sieg**

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1 Introduction to ERL Professional

The objective of the European Robotics League is to organize several indoor robot competition events per year, ensuring a scientific competition format, around the following two challenges: ERL Consumer and ERL Professional. Those indoor robot competitions will be focused on two major challenges addressed by H2020: societal challenges (service robots helping and interacting with humans at home, especially the elderly and those with motor disabilities) and industrial leadership (industrial robots addressing the flexible factories of the future and modern automation issues). These challenges were addressed by RoCKIn and RockEU2 and will be extended in the European Robotics League by building on the current version of the rule books and testbeds designed and used during RockEU2's project lifetime.

In the ERL Professional competition, robots will assist in a small candies shop with the assembly of custom chocolate boxes. Tasks include mapping, locating, transporting and placement, checking their quality and preparing them to be delivered to customers. By combining the versatility of human workers and the accuracy, reliability and robustness of mobile robot assistants, the entire production process is able to be optimized. The ERL Professional competition is looking to make these innovative flexible manufacturing systems, such as that required by the candies shop, a reality.

This document gives general descriptions of the task benchmarks and the functional benchmarks that make up ERL Professional. The audience for the current document are teams who want to participate in the competition, the organizers of events where the ERL Professional competition is supposed to be executed, and the developers of simulation software, who want to provide their customers and users with ready-to-use models of the environment.

The remainder of this document is structured as follows:

The *testbed* for ERL Professional competitions is described in some detail in the next section (Section 2). Subsections are devoted to the specification of the structure of the environment and its properties (Section 2.1), to the mechanical parts and objects in the environment which can be manipulated (Section 2.2), to objects in the environment that need to be recognized for completing the task (Section 2.2), to the networked devices embedded in the environment and accessible to the robot (Section 2.3), and to the benchmarking equipment which we plan to install in the environment and which may impose additional constraints to the robot's behavior (equipment presenting obstacles to avoid) or add further perceptual noise (visible equipment, see Section 2.5). Next (Section 3), we provide some specifications and constraints applying to the *robots and teams* permitted to participate in ERL Professional. The European Robotics League consortium is striving to minimize such constraints, but for reasons of safety and practicality such constraints are required. After that, the next two sections describe in detail the *task benchmarks* (Section 4) and the *functionality benchmarks* (Section 5) comprising the ERL Professional competition, while information on scoring and ranking the performance of participating teams on each benchmark is already provided in the benchmark descriptions. Section 6, *award categories* surveys the number and kind of awards that will be awarded and how the ranking of the award categories is determined based on individual benchmark results. Last but not least, Section 7 provides details on *organizational issues*, like the committees involved, the media to communicate with teams, qualification and setup procedures, competition schedules, and post-competition activities.

2 The ERL Professional Testbed

The testbed for the ERL Professional competition consists of the arena (e.g. walls, workstation), networked devices and task-related objects. The robot can communicate and interact with the networked devices, which allow the robot to exert control on the testbed to a certain extent. Figure 1 shows the evolution of the ERL Professional environment from its early concept in RoCKIn@Work to its implementation in the RoCKIn@Work event in Lisbon in 2015 and RockEU2 event in Polimi in 2017. Participating teams should assume the competition environment to be similar to those shown in Figure 1; deviations should only occur if on-site constraints (space available, safety regulations) enforce them.

Figure 1: The evolution of the ERL Professional environment. Photo Credits: ERL

2.1 Environment Structure and Properties

The following set of scenario specifications must be met by the ERL Professional environment.

Environment Specification 2.1 (*Structured Environment*)

The environment can consist of various numbers of spatial areas:

1. rows of shelves
2. rows of workstations

Figure 7 shows an example of these areas in the ERL Professional environment. The spatial areas extend beyond the space occupied by the respective workstations or objects and include the surrounding area as well.

Environment Specification 2.2 (*Flat Environment*)

All spatial areas are located on the same level, except where specified otherwise. There are no stairs in the environment.

Environment Specification 2.3 (*Spatial Areas and Rooms*)

The factory is a single, large open space; there are no rooms separated by walls in the environment. Spatial areas can be partially separated by dividing or protective walls or other objects present in the factory (e.g. shelves, workstations, platforms, tables).

Figure 2: Example of the spatial areas in the ERL Professional environment. The spatial areas are shelves (red) and assembly workstation (yellow). Photo Credits: ERL

Environment Specification 2.4 (*Dimensions*)

The precise dimensions and the arrangement of the spatial areas are not predefined, but estimated sizes are given. The estimated sizes of the spatial areas are as follows: workstations $2m \times 2m$ and shelves $5m \times 0,5m$. The bounding box of the environment has a minimum area of $16m^2$ and a maximum area of $100m^2$. More space is used, when areas and workstations are doubled for teams working in parallel.

Environment Specification 2.5 (*Set of Shelves*)

The shelves-area is a set of connected shelves and each shelves has two level (upper level and lower level). The robot can take and/or deliver objects from the shelves (through the containers or directly onto shelves). Figure 7 shows an example of the shelves-area made from two set of shelves.

Environment Specification 2.6 (*Workstations*)

Workstations are used as storage areas for objects. They may be accessible from different locations, i.e. it might be possible to reach a workstation from two or more sides. Additionally, there are workstations of different heights present in the environment, ranging from 0 cm up to 60 cm. If a workstation has a height of 0 cm, a tape will mark the area (see Figure 4). The tape will be taped on the floor and is blue/white striped. This tape may be crossed by the robot and does not count as a collision.

Environment Specification 2.7 (*Barrier Tape as Virtual Walls*)

The environment may include virtual walls marked by either striped yellow/black or white/red barrier tape on the floor (see Figure 5). If any part of a robot passes over such a tape it is considered as a collision with an obstacle. The red/white tape is used to frame the entrance

Figure 3: Shelves

Figure 4: Barrier tape used to mark workstations with 0 cm height.

and exit area. The robot is allowed to cross this kind of barrier only at the beginning of a test to enter arena and at the end for leaving. In contrast, the yellow/black one denotes an obstacle which the robot is never allowed to cross.

Figure 5: Example of the different kind of barrier tapes. The red/white tape is used for the entrance and exit, while the yellow/black one denotes an obstacle. Photo credit: b-it-bots

2.2 Objects in the Environment

The test bed environment will contain numerous objects. These objects needs to be perceived and manipulated. This section contains specifications and restrictions for selecting these objects.

Object Specification 2.1 (*Perception-Relevant Object Types*)

These are objects that the robot must only be able to perceive. By perceive we mean that the robot should be able to recognize if such an object is in its view, that it should be able to identify the object if it is unique or to classify it if not (e.g. an instance of a cup, if several non-unique instances exist), and that it should be able to localize the object. Objects that are only perception-relevant usually occur in tasks where the robot is supposed to find and localize these objects, but is not required to manipulate them. The perception-relevant objects in the environment include the following types of objects:

- The basic environment structure including floors, walls, and ceilings.
- Containers for keeping objects inside.

Object Specification 2.2 (*Manipulation-Relevant Object Types*)

The manipulation-relevant object types that can be used during the tournament are:

- RoboCup objects
- T-LESS dataset objects
- Chocolates

Object Specification 2.3 (*RoboCup Objects*)

RoboCup objects to be used include:

- Bearing Box
- Bearing
- F20_20_G
- F20_20_B
- S40_40_G
- S40_40_B
- M20_100
- R20
- Motor
- Axis
- Distance Tube
- M20
- M30

Table 1: List of parts to be manipulated, Photo Credits: RoboCup@work

Object	Symbolic Description
--------	----------------------

	Bearing_Box
	Bearing
	Axis
	Distance_Tube
	Motor
	F20_20_B
	F20_20_G

	S40_40_B
	S40_40_G
	M20_100
	M20
	M30
	R20

Object Specification 2.4 (*Chocolates*)

Chocolates to be used include:

- *Pickup! Black'n White[®]*
- *Pickup! Choco Milk[®]*
- *duplo White[®]*
- *duplo Classic[®]*
- *Twix Spekulatius[®]*
- *Twix White[®]*
- *Twix Classic[®]*
- *Twix Mini[®]*
- *Mars[®]*
- *Mars Mini[®]*

Figure 6: RoboCup objects, Photo Credits: ERL

- *Snickers*[®]
- *Snickers Mini*[®]
- *KitKat Classic*[®]
- *KitKat White*[®]
- *KitKat Chunky White*[®]
- *KitKat Chunky Classic*[®]
- *KitKat Mini*[®]
- *Lion Classic*[®]
- *Lion Mini*[®]
- *M&M's Cripsy*[®]
- *M&M's Peanut*[®]
- *Bounty*[®]
- *Bounty Mini*[®]
- *Milkyway*[®]
- *Milkyway Mini*[®]
- *Rittersport Nugat*[®]

- Rittersport Knusperkeks[®]
- Rittersport Joghurt[®]
- Rittersport Knusperflakes[®]
- Rittersport Nuss Splitter[®]
- Rittersport Marzipan[®]
- Rittersport Edel Vollmilch[®]

Note: The copyrights and the trademarks of the names mentioned above belong to the respective copyright holders. We are using them for representational purpose only.

Figure 7: Chocolate objects, Photo Credits: ERL

Object Specification 2.5 (*T-LESS Objects*)

The *T-LESS* objects don't have specific names. They are just numbered from 1 to 30.

Object Constraint 2.1 (*Object Mass*)

The objects foreseen for manipulation can have a maximum mass of 300 g.

Object Constraint 2.2 (*Object Size*)

The default minimum width/length/depth/diameter/thickness (henceforth: *size*) of an object foreseen for manipulation is 1 cm, and the default sum of the length, width, and height of the smallest bounding box around the object 3 cm (henceforth: *box sum*). An object may have a lower size than 2 cm, down to 5 mm, in up to two dimensions, if the other dimensions compensate for it, i.e. if the box sum is still at least 3 cm. The maximum size of an object

Figure 8: T-LESS dataset objects Photo Credits: <http://cmp.felk.cvut.cz/t-less/>

foreseen for manipulation is 10 cm and the default maximum box size is 20 cm.

Object Constraint 2.3 (*Object Content*)

Objects may not consist of or contain any kind of hazardous material.

2.3 Networked Devices in the Environment

There are various networked devices available in the ERL Professional environment. The following description provides an overview on the capability of each networked device. An interface description for each networked device is provided in detail in the task benchmark section (see Section 4). Both networked devices are used for delivering parts to the ERL Professional arena and they are operated by the referee(s).

(a) Conveyor belt

(b) Rotating table

Figure 9: Networked devices within the ERL Professional environment. Photo Credits: ERL

2.4 Central Factory Hub

The main idea of the ERL Professional testbed software infrastructure is to have a central server-like hub (the ERL Professional Central Factory Hub) that serves all the services that are needed for executing and scoring tasks and successfully realize the competition. This hub is derived from software systems well known in industrial business (e.g. SAP). It provides the robots with information regarding the specific tasks and tracks the production process as well as stock and logistics information of the candies shop. It is a plug-in driven software system. Each plug-in is responsible for a specific task, benchmarking or other functionality.

The following set of specifications must be met by the ERL Professional Central Factory Hub(CFH).

CFH Specification 2.1 (*Central Factory Hub*)

Central managing of all services needed for controlling data, devices and robots. In the following paragraphs, several plug-in will be described. In future, a web-based user interface would be useful.

CFH Specification 2.2 (*Benchmarking Plug-in*)

A plug-in to serve general benchmark functionalities or interact with a separated BM software.

CFH Specification 2.3 (*Production Tracking Database Plug-in*)

An automatic plug-in with the central database tracking all identifiers, status of finished products, sub-assemblies, stock level etc.

The CFH-related sources and client example can be obtained from the following locations:

- CFH: https://github.com/industrial-robotics/atwork_central_factory_hub
- Client example: https://github.com/industrial-robotics/atwork_refbox_ros_client

2.5 Benchmarking Equipment in the Environment

ERL Professional benchmarking is based on the processing of data collected in two ways:

- **internal benchmarking data**, collected by the robot system under test (see Section 3);
- **external benchmarking data**, collected by the equipment embedded into the testbed.

External benchmarking data is generated by the ERL Professional testbed with a multitude of methods, depending on their nature.

One of the types of external benchmarking data used by ERL Professional are pose data about robots and/or their constituent parts. To acquire these, ERL Professional uses a camera-based commercial motion capture system (e.g. NaturalPoint OptiTrack), composed of dedicated hardware and software. Benchmarking data has the form of a time series of poses of rigid elements of the robot (such as the base or the wrist). There is a case where the motion capture system influences the robot perception system. It is the teams' responsibility to check this effect and coordinate with the benchmarking team in order to minimize this effect. Once generated by the OptiTrack system, pose data are acquired and logged by a customized external software system based on ROS (Robot Operating System): more precisely, logged data is saved as *bagfiles* created with the *rosvbag* utility provided by ROS. Pose data is especially significant because it is used for multiple benchmarks. There are other types of external benchmarking data that ERL Professional acquires: however, these are usually collected using devices that are specific to the benchmark. For this reason, such devices are described in the context of the associated benchmark, rather than here.

Finally, equipment to collect external benchmarking data includes any *server* which is part of the testbed and that the robot subjected to a benchmark has to access as part of the benchmark. Communication between servers and robot is performed via the testbed's own wireless network (see Section 3.2).

3 Robots and Teams

The purpose of this section is twofold:

1. It specifies information about various robot features that can be derived from the environment and the targeted tasks. These features are to be considered at least as desirable, if not required for a proper solution of the task. Nevertheless, we will try to leave the design space for solutions as large as possible and to avoid premature and unjustified constraints.
2. The robot features specified here should be supplied in detail for any robot participating in the competition. This is necessary in order to allow better assessment of competition and benchmark results later on.

The description of the robot should be included in the team description paper.

3.1 General Specifications and Constraints on Robots and Teams

Robot Specification 3.1 (*System*)

A competing team may use a single robot or multiple robots acting as a team. It is not required that the robots are certified for industrial use. At least one of the robots entered by a team is capable of:

- *mobility and autonomous navigation.*
- *manipulate and grasp at least several different task-relevant objects. The specific kind of manipulation and grasping activity required is to be derived from the task specifications.*

The robot subsystems (mobility, manipulation and grasping) should work with the environment and objects specified in this rule book.

Robot Specification 3.2 (*Sensor Subsystems*)

*Any robot used by a team may use any kind of **onboard** sensor subsystem, provided that the sensor system is admitted for use in the general public, its operation is safe at all times, and it does not interfere with other teams or the environment infrastructure. A team may use the sensor system in the environment provided by the organizer by using a wireless communication protocol specified for such purpose. Sensor systems used for benchmarking and any other systems intended for exclusive use of the organizers are not accessible by the robot system. Teams are not allowed to modify the environment or to install their own embedded devices in the environment, e.g., additional sensors or actuators.*

Robot Specification 3.3 (*Communication Subsystems*)

*Any robot used by a team may **internally** use any kind of communication subsystem, provided that the communication system is admitted for use in the general public, its operation is safe at all times, and it does not interfere with other teams or the environment infrastructure. A robot team must be able to use the communication system provided **as part of the environment** by correctly using a protocol specified for such purpose and provided as part of the scenario.*

Robot Specification 3.4 (*Power Supply*)

Any mobile device (esp. robots) must be designed to be usable with an onboard power supply (e.g. a battery). The power supply should be sufficient to guarantee electrical autonomy for a duration exceeding the periods foreseen in the various benchmarks, before recharging of batteries is necessary. Charging of robot batteries must be done outside of the competition

environment. The team members are responsible for safe recharging of batteries. If a team plans to use inductive power transmission devices for charging the robots, they need to request permission from the event organizers in advance and at least three months before the competition. Detailed specifications about the inductive device need to be supplied with the request for permission.

Robot Constraint 3.1 (*Computational Subsystems*)

Any robot or device used by a team as part of their solution approach must be suitably equipped with computational devices (such as onboard PCs, microcontrollers, or similar) with sufficient computational power to ensure safe autonomous operation. Robots and other devices may use external computational facilities, including Internet services and cloud computing to provide richer functionalities, but the safe operation of robots and devices may not depend on the availability of communication bandwidth and the status of external services.

Robot Constraint 3.2 (*Safety and Security Aspects*)

For any device a team brings into the environment and/or the team area, and which features at least one actuator of any kind (mobility subsystems, robot manipulators, grasping devices, actuated sensors, signal-emitting devices, etc.), a mechanism must be provided to immediately stop its operation in case of an emergency (emergency stop). For any device a team brings into the environment and/or the team area, it must guarantee safe and secure operation at all times. Event officials must be instructed about the means to stop such devices operating and how to switch them off in case of emergency situations.

Robot Constraint 3.3 (*Operation*)

In the competition, the robot should perform the tasks autonomously. An external device is allowed for additional computational power. It must be clear at all times that no manual or remote control is exerted to influence the behavior of the robots during the execution of tasks.

Robot Constraint 3.4 (*Environmental Aspects*)

Robots, devices, and apparatus causing pollution of air, such as combustion engines, or other mechanisms using chemical processes impacting the air, are not allowed. Robots, devices, and any apparatus used should minimize noise pollution. In particular, very loud noise as well as well-audible constant noises (humming, etc.) should be avoided. The regulations of the country in which a competition or benchmark is taking place must be obeyed at all times. The event organizers will provide specific information in advance, if applicable. Robots, devices, and any apparatus used should not be the cause of effects that are perceived as a nuisance to humans in the environment. Examples of such effects include causing wind and drafts, strong heat sources or sinks, stenches, or sources for allergic reactions.

3.2 Benchmarking Equipment in the Robots

Preliminary Remark: Whenever teams are required to install some element provided by ERL Professional on (or in) their robots, such element will be carefully chosen in order to minimize the work required from teams and the impact on robot performance.

Hardware As a general rule, ERL Professional does not require that teams install additional robotic hardware on their robots. Moreover, permanent change to the robot's hardware is never required. However, ERL Professional may require that additional standard PC hardware (such as an external, USB-connected hard disk for logging) is temporarily added to the robot in order to collect internal benchmarking data. When this is the case, the additional hardware is provided

by ERL Professional during the competition, and its configuration for use is either automatically performed by the operating system, or very simple.

To allow the acquisition of external benchmarking data about their pose, robots need to be fitted with special reflective markers, mounted in known positions. The teams will be required to prepare their robots to ease the mounting of the markers. Teams will be required to provide the geometric transformation from the position of the marker to the odometric center of the robot¹.

Software ERL Professional may require that robots run ERL Professional-provided (or publicly available) software during benchmarks. A typical example of such software is a package that logs data provided by the robot, or a client that interfaces with a ERL Professional server via the wireless network of the testbed. Whenever a team is required to install and run such a package, it will be provided as source code, its usage will be most simple, and complete instruction for installation and use will be provided along with it. All ERL Professional software is written to have a minimal impact on the performance of a robot, both in terms of required processing power and in terms of (lack of) interaction with other modules. When required by a benchmark, the relevant ERL Professional software to be run by participating robots is provided well in advance with respect to the competition.

ERL Professional will make any effort to avoid imposing constraints on the teams participating to the competition in terms of software architecture of their robots. This means that any provided piece of software will be designed to have the widest generality of application. However, this does not mean that the difficulty of incorporating such software into the software architecture of a robot will be independent from such architecture: for technical reasons, differences may emerge. A significant example is that of software for data logging. At the moment, it appears likely that any such software by ERL Professional will be based on the established *rosvag* software tool, library and file format. As *rosvag* is part of ROS (Robot Operating System), robots based on ROS can use it to log data without any modification; on the contrary, robots not using ROS will be required to employ the *rosvag* library to create *rosvag* files (*bagfiles*) or to develop ad-hoc code to convert their well established logging format into the *rosvag* one by using the *rosvag* API. If this will be the case, ERL Professional will provide tools to ease the introduction of software modules for creation of *bagfiles* into any software architecture; yet, teams not using ROS will probably have to perform some additional work to use such tools.

3.3 Robot Communication with Benchmarking Equipment

For some types of internal benchmarking data (i.e. provided by the robot), logging is done on board the robot, and data are collected after the benchmark (for instance, via USB stick). Other types of internal benchmarking data, instead, are communicated by the robot to the testbed during the benchmark. In such cases, communication is done by interfacing the robot with standard wireless network devices (e.g. IEEE 802.11n) that are part of the testbed, and which therefore become a part of the benchmarking equipment of the testbed. However, it must be noted that network equipment is not strictly dedicated to benchmarking: for some benchmarks, in fact, the WLAN may be (or exclusively) used to perform interaction between the robot and the testbed.

Due to the need to communicate with the testbed via the WLAN, all robots participating to the ERL Professional competition are required to:

1. possess a fully functional IEEE 802.11n network interface²;

¹Benchmarking data related to poses will refer to the marker position: this is why additional information is required to know the position of the base.

²It must be stressed that full functionality requires that the network interface must not be hampered by electromagnetic obstacles, for instance by mounting it within a metal structure and/or by employing inadequate antenna arrangements. Network spectrum in the competition area is typically very crowded, and network equipment with

2. be able to keep the wireless network interface permanently connected to the testbed WLAN for the whole duration of the benchmarks.

3.4 YAML Data File Specification

The subsequent paragraphs specify the YAML file format that can be converted to ROS bag files. This closely follows the data items described in D-2.1.7 [1]. The YAML format was chosen because it is a simple format, easy to produce without using any special library. Furthermore, the ROS messages format is already defined: as produced by the `rostopic echo` command.

3.4.1 File Format

The YAML file should be composed of a single list of messages. Each message should have four items:

- `topic` - The topic name.
- `secs` - Timestamp of the message, in number of seconds since 1970.
- `nsecs` - Nanoseconds component of the timestamp.
- `message` - The message, according to the topic type.

The message should be formatted in YAML, according to its structure. This is the same as the output of `rostopic echo`. However, binary fields may be specified in base 64 encoding for much smaller files. You can copy the file `src/base64.hpp` to your project, it depends only on boost to encode base 64.

And example for a file generated according to above specification could look as follows:

```
- topic: pose2d
  secs: 1397024209
  nsecs: 156423000
  message:
    x: 5.5
    y: 6
    theta: 6.4
- topic: image
  secs: 1397024210
  nsecs: 53585000
  message:
    header:
      seq: 306
      stamp:
        secs: 1397024210
        nsecs: 53585000
      frame_id: ''
    height: 4
    width: 4
    encoding: bgr8
    is_bigendian: 0
    step: 12
    data:
      !!binary JaU8JY0kGXUIAZOUDWzgAXjgAb0kIglwbkGsnkWwoiWUfiGUhi2olhmUgc1YRaUw
```

impaired radio capabilities may not be capable of accessing the testbed WLAN, even if correctly working in less critical conditions.

3.4.2 YAML-to-ROSBAG Conversion Tool

A tool to convert European Robotics League YAML files into ROS bag files is available at the RoCKIn Github repository:

`https://github.com/rockin-robot-challenge/benchmark_and_scoring_converter`

4 Task Benchmarks

Details concerning rules, procedures, as well as scoring and benchmarking methods, are common to all task benchmarks.

Rules and Procedures Every run of each of the task benchmark will be preceded by a safety-check, outlined as follows:

1. The team members must ensure and inform at least one of the organizing committee (OC) member, present during the execution of the task, that they have an emergency stop button on the robot which is fully functional. Any member of the OC can ask the team to stop their robot at any time which must be done immediately.
2. A member of the OC present during the execution of the task will make sure that the robot complies with the other safety-related rules and robot specifications presented in Section 3.

All teams are required to perform each task according to the steps mentioned in the rules and procedures sub-subsections for the tasks. During the competition, all teams are required to repeat the task benchmarks several times. On the last day, only a selected number of top teams will be allowed to perform the task benchmarks again. Maximum time allowed for one task benchmark is 10 minutes.

Acquisition of Benchmarking Data Following some general notes on the acquisition of benchmarking data are described. They are valid for all task benchmarks, as well as for the functional benchmarks.

- **Calibration parameters** Important! Calibration parameters for cameras must be saved. This must be done for other sensors (e.g., Kinect) that require calibration as well, if a calibration procedure has been applied instead of using the default values (e.g., those provided by OpenNI).
- **Notes on data saving** The specific data that the robot must save is described in the benchmark section. In general some data streams (those with the highest bitrate) must be logged only in the time intervals when they are actually used by the robot to perform the activities required by the benchmark. In this way, system load and data bulk are minimized. For instance, whenever a benchmark includes object recognition activities, video and point cloud data must be logged by the robot only in the time intervals when it is actually performing object recognition.
- **Use of data** The logged data is not used during the competition. In particular, it is not used for scoring. The data is processed by European Robotics League consortium members after the end of the competition. It is used for in-depth analysis and/or to produce datasets to be published for the benefit of the robotics community.
- **Where and when to save data** Robots must save the data as specified in the section “Acquisition of Benchmarking Data” of their respective TBM/FBM on a USB stick provided by ERL Professional staff. The USB stick is given to the team immediately before the start of the benchmark, and must be returned (with the required data on it) at the end of the benchmark. Each time a teams robot executes a benchmark, the team must:
 1. Create, in the root directory of the USB stick, a new directory named
 - NameOfTheTeam_FBMx_DD_HH-MM (for FBM) or
 - NameOfTheTeam_TBMx_DD_HH-MM (for TBM)
 2. Configure the robot to save the data files in these directories.

In the filenames above x denotes the number of the benchmark, DD is the day of the month and HH , MM represent the time of the day (hours and minutes).

All files produced by the robot that are associated with the execution of the benchmark must be written in this directory. Please note that a new directory must be created for each benchmark executed by the robot. This holds true even when the benchmark is a new run of one that the robot already executed.

During the execution of the benchmark, the following data will be collected³. In brackets the expected ROS topics are named. Corresponding data types can be stored in a YAML file (see Section 3.4) or rosbag. Following the list of **offline data** to be logged:

Topic	Type	Frame Id	Notes
/rockin/robot_pose ⁴	geometry_msgs/PoseStamped	/map	10 Hz
/rockin/marker_pose ⁵	geometry_msgs/PoseStamped	/map	10 Hz
/rockin/trajectory ⁶	nav_msgs/Path	/map	Each (re)plan
/rockin/<device>/image ⁷	sensor_msgs/Image	/<device>_frame	–
/rockin/<device>/camera_info ⁸	sensor_msgs/CameraInfo	–	–
/rockin/depth_<id>/pointcloud ⁹	sensor_msgs/PointCloud2	/depth_<id>_frame	–
/rockin/scan_<id> ¹⁰	sensor_msgs/LaserScan	/laser_<id>_frame	10-40Hz
tf ¹¹	tf	–	–

Some robots might not have some of the sensors or they might have multiple instances of the previous data (e.g., multiple rgb cameras or multiple laser scanner), in this case you append the number of the device to the topic and the frame (e.g., /erlir/scan_0 in /laser_frame_0). It is possible not to log some of the data, if the task does not require it.

The **online** data part can be found in the description of the respective benchmark.

Communication with CFH The following steps describe the part of the CFH communication that is applicable for all TBMs.

1. The robot sends a **BeaconSignal** message at least every second.
2. The robot waits for **BenchmarkState** messages. It starts the benchmark execution when the *phase* field is equal to EXECUTION and the *state* field is equal to RUNNING.
3. The robot waits for an **Inventory** message from the CFH (which is continuously sent out by the CFH) in order to receive the initial distribution of objects and their locations in the environment.

³In the following, ‘offline’ identifies data produced by the robot, and stored locally on the robot, that will be collected by the referees when the execution of the benchmark ends (e.g., as files on a USB stick), while ‘online’ identifies data that the robot has to transmit to the CFH during the execution of the benchmark. Data marked neither with ‘offline’ nor ‘online’ is generated outside the robot.

⁴The 2D robot pose at the floor level, i.e., $z = 0$ and only yaw rotation.

⁵The 3D pose of the marker in 6 degrees of freedom.

⁶Trajectories planned by the robot including when replanning.

⁷Image processed for object perception; <device> must be any of stereo_left, stereo_right, rgb; if multiple devices of type <device> are available on your robot, you can append "_0", "_1", and so on to the device name: e.g., "rgb_0", "stereo_left_2", and so on.

⁸Calibration info for /erlir/<device>/image.

⁹Point cloud processed for object perception; <id> is a counter starting from 0 to take into account the fact that multiple depth camera could be present on the robot: e.g., "depth_0", "depth_1", and so on.

¹⁰Laser scans, <id> is a counter starting from 0 to take into account the fact that multiple laser range finders could be present on the robot: e.g., "scan_0", "scan_1", and so on.

¹¹The tf topic on the robot; the tf tree needs to contain the frames described in this table properly connected through the /base_frame which is the odometric center of the robot.

4. The robot waits for an **Order** message from the CFH (which is sent out continuously by the CFH) in order to receive the actual task, i.e., where the objects should be at the end.
5. The task benchmark ends when all objects are at their final location as specified in the **Order** message. After that the robot sends a message of type **BenchmarkFeedback** to the CFH with the *phase_to_terminate* field set to EXECUTION. The robot should do this until the **BenchmarkState**'s *state* field has changed.

The messages to be sent and to be received can be seen on the Github repository located at [2].

Scoring and Ranking Evaluation of the performance of a robot according to this task benchmark is based on performance equivalence classes and they are related to the fact that the robot has done the required task or not.

The criterion defining the performance equivalence class of robots is based on the concept of *tasks required achievements*. While the ranking of the robot within each equivalence class is obtained by looking at the performance criteria. In particular:

- The performance of any robot belonging to performance class N is considered as better than the performance of any robot belonging to performance class M whenever $M < N$
- Considering two robots belonging to the same class, then a penalization criterion (penalties are defined according to task performance criteria) is used and the performance of the one which received less penalizations is considered as better
- If the two robots received the same amount of penalizations, the performance of the one which finished the task more quickly is considered as better (unless not being able to reach a given achievement within a given time is explicitly considered as a penalty).

Performance equivalence classes and in-class ranking of the robots are determined according to three sets:

- A set A of **achievements**, i.e., things that should happen (what the robot is expected to do).
- A set PB of **penalized behaviors**, i.e., robot behaviors that are penalized, if they happen, (e.g., hitting furniture).
- A set DB of **disqualifying behaviors**, i.e., robot behaviors that absolutely must not happen (e.g., hitting people).

Scoring is implemented with the following 3-step sorting algorithm:

1. If one or more of the elements of set DB occur during task execution, the robot gets disqualified (i.e. assigned to the lowest possible performance class, called class 0), and no further scoring procedures are performed.
2. Performance equivalence class X is assigned to the robot, where X corresponds to the number of achievements in set A that have been accomplished.
3. Whenever an element of set PB occurs, a penalization is assigned to the robot (without changing its performance class).

One key property of this scoring system is that a robot that executes the required task completely will always be placed into a higher performance class than a robot that executes the task partially. Moreover the penalties do not make a robot change class (also in the case of incomplete task).

Penalized Behaviors and Disqualifying Behaviors The penalizing behaviors for all task benchmarks are:

- The robot collides with obstacles in the testbed.
- The robot drops an object.
- The robot stops working.
- The robot accidentally place an object on top of another object.

The disqualifying behaviors for all task benchmarks are:

- The robot damages or destroys the objects requested to manipulate.
- The robot damages the testbed.

The achievements for each task are unique and are described in the respective task benchmark section.

4.1 Task *Pick from a Box*

This task reflects one of the primary requisites of a mobile robotic service assistant, i.e., to work together with humans. In this case the goal is to assist humans at a manual assembly workstation. Most of the industrial and work areas have object placed inside containers large or small. The task here is to pick a multiple objects from inside a container.

4.1.1 Task Description

The robot has to pick up several objects from inside a container on a single source locations and deliver them to a single destination location. On start of the run the robot is informed of the inventory and the order. The inventory contains information about the current state of the objects in the arena while the order contains information about the final state of the objects. Based on these information the robot should plan series of actions to pick and place the objects as per the order in the restricted time. In this task all the objects are located inside a container. There maybe a case that the object is hidden and not visible by direct sight.

Figure 10: ERL Professional container with objects. Photo Credits: ERL

4.1.2 Feature Variation

All objects defined in Section 2.2 will be used in this task. Several containers (see Section 2.2) can be present in the environment and are always associated with a workstation or shelf. It

is possible that more than one container is placed on top of a single workstation. Currently, a container itself does not need to be manipulated or transported by the robot.

For any major competition in which ERL Professional will be present, additional objects may be used. Those objects can be found in the rule descriptions of the major competition (e.g. for RoboCup)

4.1.3 Input Provided

The teams must create a map of the arena, during the set-up days, and label it with different locations for manipulation. The names of different objects and locations will be distributed to the teams before the competition. The following information about the object and object locations are provided before the run

- The list of possible parts used in the task;
- The list of source service areas
- The list of destination service areas

4.1.4 Expected Robot Behavior or Output

The task execution is triggered by the robot receiving the inventory and order list from the CFH. The robot proceeds with collecting the parts from the source locations and transports them to the destination service areas. At any instance the robot can only carry a maximum of 3 objects.

4.1.5 Procedures and Rules

The maximum time allowed for one functionality run is 5 minutes (30 seconds for preparation and 210 seconds for execution). A run consists of (1) a preparation phase where the teams can prepare the robots and (2) an execution phase in which the robot plans its actions based on order.

Step 1 The robot will receive an order and inventory from the CFH containing a list of objects to be collected and delivered.

Step 2 The robot must plan the best path to the designated workstation, passing through each storage area where the required objects for a requested product in the list can be found.

Step 3 The robot must execute the above path, collect the objects and then deliver them to the designated destination locations.

Step 4 The Steps 2 and 3 above must be done for all the objects in the list mentioned above in Step 1.

4.1.6 Communication with CFH

For this task benchmark the robot does not have to control any networked device in the environment. Thus, the robot is only supposed to receive the static inventory and order information once. Currently, the robot does not need to update the inventory information.

4.1.7 Acquisition of Benchmarking Data

General information on the acquisition of benchmarking data is described in Section 4.

Online Data

- No online benchmarking data has to be sent to the CFH during this task benchmark.

Offline data The additional information described in the following table has to be logged:

Topic	Type	Frame Id	Notes
/rockin/notification ¹²	std_msgs/String	–	–

4.1.8 Scoring and Ranking

Evaluation of the performance of a robot according to this task benchmark is based on performance equivalence classes. Classes are defined in dependence to the number of parts of the product to be assembled actually provided by the robot to the human worker and their order according to the desired one.

Achievements The set A of achievements for this task consists of:

- The robot communicates with the CFH throughout the test;
- The team submits the benchmarking data by the end of the test;
- The robot picks up a required object from its storage location;
- The robot places the required objects in its destination area;
- The robot has correctly collected and delivered all objects

4.2 Task *Fill a Box with Parts for Manual Assembly*

This task reflects one of the primary requisites of a mobile robotic service assistant, i.e., to work together with humans. In this case the goal is to assist humans at a manual assembly workstation. The robots have to deal with flexible task specifications, especially concerning information about object constellations in source and target locations, and task constraints such as limits on the number of objects allowed to be carried simultaneously, etc.

4.2.1 Task Description

The robot has to pick up several parts from different source locations and deliver them to several destination locations. On start of the run the robot is informed of the inventory and the order. The inventory contains information about the current state of the objects in the arena while the order contains information about the final state of the objects. Based on these information the robot should plan series of actions to pick and place the objects as per the order in the restricted time. Some order needs to be placed inside containers for which the robot should identify those containers in the arena. At any instance the robot can carry only 3 objects.

4.2.2 Feature Variation

All objects defined in Section 2.2 will be used in this task. Several containers (see Section 2.2) can be present in the environment and are always associated with a workstation or shelf. It is possible that more than one container is placed on top of a single workstation. Currently, a container itself does not need to be manipulated or transported by the robot.

For any major competition in which ERL Professional will be present, additional objects may be used. Those objects can be found in the rule descriptions of the major competition (e.g. for RoboCup)

¹²The string with the notification of the perceived object should be in a tab separated string: CLASS OBJECT_ID X Y THETA

4.2.3 Input Provided

The teams must create a map of the arena, during the set-up days, and label it with different locations for manipulation. The names of different objects and locations will be distributed to the teams before the competition. The following information about the object and object locations are provided before the run

- The list of possible objects used in the task
- The list of source service areas
- The list of destination service areas

4.2.4 Expected Robot Behavior or Output

The task execution is triggered by the robot receiving the inventory and order list from the CFH. The robot proceeds with collecting the parts from the source locations and transports them to the destination service areas. At any instance the robot can only carry a maximum of 3 objects.

4.2.5 Procedures and Rules

There can be multiple obstacles and barrier tapes (color: yellow/black) present in the environment that might block the direct path of the competing robot. The robot must avoid all obstacles or even other robots during the execution of the complete task.

The maximum time allowed for one functionality run is 5 minutes (30 seconds for preparation and 210 seconds for execution). A run consists of (1) a preparation phase where the teams can prepare the robots and (2) an execution phase in which the robot plans its actions based on order.

Step 1 The robot will receive an order and inventory from the CFH containing a list of objects to be collected and delivered.

Step 2 The robot must plan the best path to the designated workstation, passing through each storage area where the required objects for a requested product in the list can be found.

Step 3 The robot must execute the above path, collect the objects and then deliver them to the designated destination locations.

Step 4 The Steps 2 and 3 above must be done for all the objects in the list mentioned above in Step 1.

4.2.6 Communication with CFH

For this task benchmark the robot does not have to control any networked device in the environment. Thus, the robot is only supposed to receive the static inventory and order information once. Currently, the robot does not need to update the inventory information.

4.2.7 Acquisition of Benchmarking Data

General information on the acquisition of benchmarking data is described in Section 4.

Online Data

- No online benchmarking data has to be sent to the CFH during this task benchmark.

Topic	Type	Frame Id	Notes
/rockin/notification ¹³	std_msgs/String	-	-

Offline data The additional information described in the following table has to be logged:

4.2.8 Scoring and Ranking

Evaluation of the performance of a robot according to this task benchmark is based on performance equivalence classes. Classes are defined in dependence to the number of parts of the product to be assembled actually provided by the robot to the human worker and their order according to the desired one.

Achievements The set A of achievements for this task consists of:

- The robot communicates with the CFH throughout the test;
- The team submits the benchmarking data by the end of the test;
- The robot picks up a required object from its storage location;
- The robot places the required objects in its destination area;
- The robot has correctly collected and delivered all objects

¹³The string with the notification of the perceived object should be in a tab separated string: CLASS OBJECT_ID X Y THETA

5 Functionality Benchmarks

Communication with CFH Every functionality benchmark will be preceded by a safety-check similar to that described for the task benchmark procedures. All teams are required to perform each functionality benchmark according to the steps mentioned in their respective section. During the competition, all teams are required to repeat it the functionality benchmark several times. On the last day, only a selected number of top teams will be allowed to perform it.

The following steps describe the part of the CFH communication that is applicable for all FBMs.

1. The robot sends a **BeaconSignal** message at least every second.
2. The robot waits for **BenchmarkState** messages. It starts the benchmark execution when the *phase* field is equal to PREPARATION and the *state* field is equal to RUNNING.
3. As soon as the robot finishes the preparation phase, it sends a message of type **BenchmarkFeedback** to the CFH with the *phase to terminate* field set to PREPARATION.
4. The robot waits for a **BenchmarkState** message. It starts the benchmark execution when the *phase* field is equal to EXECUTION and the *state* field is equal to RUNNING.
5. As soon as the robot has finished the FBM, it sends a message of type BenchmarkFeedback to the CFH with the required results and the *phase to terminate* field set to EXECUTION.
6. The robot continues with Step 2.
7. The functionality benchmark ends when the robot receives a **BenchmarkState** message with *phase* field is equal to EXECUTION and the state field is equal to FINISHED.

Figure 11: Communication with the CFH, source: ERL

The messages to be sent and to be received can be seen on the Github repository located at [2].

5.1 Object Perception Functionality

5.1.1 Functionality Description

This functionality benchmark evaluates the capabilities of a robot to extract information about observed objects. Objects presented to the robot in this functionality benchmark are based on the the ERL Professional factory scenario. Teams are provided with a list of objects (object instances), subdivided into classes before the tournament. In this benchmark, the robot is expected to detect and estimate the object’s class and identity. Objects that are used here are described in Section 2.2.

Figure 12: Object Perception Functionality. Photo Credits: ERL

5.1.2 Feature Variation

For this benchmark, the variation space for object features is represented by the (known) set of objects that the robot may be presented with. Variation space for object location is the surface of the benchmarking area where objects are located (see Section 5.1.3).

5.1.3 Input Provided

The set of individual objects that will actually be presented to the robot during the execution of the functionality benchmark is a subset of a larger set of available objects (“object instances”). Object instances are subdivided into classes of objects that have one or more properties in common (“object classes”). Objects of the same class share one or more properties, not necessarily related to their geometry (for instance, a class may include objects that share their application domain). Each object instance and each object class is assigned a unique ID.

The team does not know which object instances will actually be presented to the robot during the benchmark. However, the team will be provided with the following information:

- Descriptions of all the object instances;
- Subdivision of the object instances into object classes (for instance: profiles, screws, joints);
- The table surface on which the objects will be placed.

Object descriptions will be expressed according to widely accepted representations, well in advance of the competition.

5.1.4 Expected Robot Behavior or Output

The objects that the robot is required to perceive are positioned, one at the time, on a table (benchmark setup area) located directly in front of the robot. The actual pose of the objects presented to the robot is unknown before they are set on the table. For each presented object, the robot must perform all of the following:

- Object detection(i.e., class recognition): perception of the presence of an object on the table and association between the perceived object and one of the object classes.
- Object recognition(i.e., instance recognition): association between the perceived object and one of the object instances belonging to the selected class.

5.1.5 Procedures and Rules

The maximum time allowed for one functionality run is 2 minutes. A run is defined as the detection, recognition and localization of one object.

Step 1 An object of unknown class and unknown instance will be placed in front of the robot

Step 2 The robot must determine the objects class, its instance within that class.

Step 3 The preceding steps are repeated until 10 runs have been completed.

5.1.6 Communication with CFH

For this functionality benchmark the robot does not have to control any networked device in the environment. Only the communication as described below is necessary:

Step 1 The robot sends a **BeaconSignal** message at least every second.

Step 2 The robot waits for a **BenchmarkState** message. It starts the benchmark execution when the *phase* field is equal to EXECUTION and the *state* field is equal to RUNNING.

Step 3 As soon as the robot has finished perceiving the object, it sends a message of type **BenchmarkFeedback** to the CFH with the required results and the *phase_to_terminate* field set to EXECUTION. The robot should do this until the **BenchmarkState**'s *state* field has changed.

Step 4 The robot continues with Step 2.

Step 5 The functionality benchmark ends when the **BenchmarkState**'s *state* field is equal to FINISHED.

The messages to be sent and to be received can be seen on the Github repository located at [2].

5.1.7 Acquisition of Benchmarking Data

General information on the acquisition of benchmarking data is described in Section 4. There, the **offline** part of the benchmarking data can be found.

Online data In order to send online benchmarking data to the CFH, the robot has to use the **BenchmarkFeedback** message. The message contains:

- `object_class_name` (type: string)
- `object_instance_name` (type: string))

The **BenchmarkFeedback** message can be found at [2].

Offline data The additional information described in the following table has to be logged:

Topic	Type	Frame Id	Notes
/rockin/notification ¹⁴	std_msgs/String	-	-

5.1.8 Scoring and Ranking

Evaluation of the performance of a robot according to this functionality benchmark is based on:

1. The number and percentage of correctly identified objects class;
2. The number and percentage of correctly identified objects object name;
3. Execution time (if less than the maximum allowed for the benchmark).

The previous criteria are in order of importance; the first criterion is applied first and teams will be scored according to their accuracy, the ties are broken by using the second one still applying accuracy metrics, and in case of ties we will resort to execution time.

5.2 Manipulation Pick Functionality

5.2.1 Functionality Description

This functionality benchmark assesses the robot's capability of grasping different objects. An object from a known set of possible objects is presented to the robot to be grasped. Once the object is successfully grasped it needs to notify the CFH.

Figure 13: Manipulation Pick Functionality. Photo Credits: b-it-bots

5.2.2 Feature Variation

The objects used in the benchmark will be selected from the list of parts to manipulate as presented in Section 2.2. Additionally, the precise position of the object differs in each test.

5.2.3 Input Provided

The team will be provided with the following information:

- The list of possible objects used in the functionality benchmark.
- Possible placement of each object used in the functionality benchmark.

¹⁴The string with the notification of the perceived object should be in a tab separated string: CLASS OBJECT_ID X Y THETA

5.2.4 Expected Robot Behaviour or Output

The robot is placed in front of the test area (a planar surface). One object will be placed in the test area and the robot will identify the object and move its end effector on top of it. Afterwards, the robot performs the grasping motion of the object and notifies that the grasping has occurred. The task is repeated with different objects. In case of failure the robot can retry the pick or can notify the CFH that the grasping failed.

5.2.5 Procedures and Rules

The maximum time allowed for one functionality run is 4 minutes (30 seconds for preparation and 210 seconds for execution). A run consists of (1) a preparation phase where the robot is going to its initial configuration and releases a previously grasp object and (2) an execution phase in which the robot detects, localizes, recognizes and manipulates one object.

Step 1 An object of unknown class and unknown instance will be placed on a table in front of the robot.

Step 2 The robot must grasp the object, lift it, and notify that grasping has occurred.

Step 3 The robot must keep the grip for a given time while the referee verifies the correct manipulation of the object.

Step 4 The preceding steps are repeated with five different objects.

For each presented object, the robot must produce the result consisting of:

- object grasped [string], e.g. true.

5.2.6 Communication with CFH

For this functionality benchmark the robot does not have to control any networked device in the environment. Only the communication as described below is necessary:

Step 1 The robot sends a **BeaconSignal** message at least every second.

Step 2 The robot waits for a **BenchmarkState** message. It starts the preparation procedure when the *phase* field is equal to PREPARATION and the *state* field is equal to RUNNING.

Step 3 As soon as the robot finishes the preparation phase, it sends a message of type **BenchmarkFeedback** to the CFH with the *phase_to_terminate* field set to PREPARATION. The robot should do this until the **BenchmarkState**'s *phase* and *state* fields have changed.

Step 4 The robot waits for a **BenchmarkState** message. It starts the benchmark execution when the *phase* field is equal to EXECUTION and the *state* field is equal to RUNNING.

Step 5 As soon as the robot has finished manipulating the object, it sends a message of type **BenchmarkFeedback** to the CFH with the required results and the *phase_to_terminate* field set to EXECUTION. The robot should do this until the **BenchmarkState**'s *phase* and *state* fields have changed.

Step 6 The robot continues with Step 2.

Step 7 The functionality benchmark ends when the **BenchmarkState**'s *phase* field is equal to EXECUTION and the *state* field is equal to FINISHED.

The messages to be sent and to be received can be seen on the Github repository located at [2].

5.2.7 Acquisition of Benchmarking Data

General information on the acquisition of benchmarking data is described in Section 4. There, the **offline** part of the benchmarking data can be found.

Online data In order to send online benchmarking data to the CFH, the robot has to use the **BenchmarkFeedback** message. The message contains:

- grasp_notification (type: bool)

The **BenchmarkFeedback** message can be found at [2].

Offline data The additional information described in the following table has to be logged:

Topic	Type	Frame Id	Notes
/rockin/grasping_pose ¹⁵	geometry_msgs/PoseStamped	/base_link	10 Hz
/rockin/gripper_pose ¹⁶	geometry_msgs/PoseStamped	/base_link	10 Hz
/rockin/arm_joints ¹⁷	geometry_msgs/JointState	/base_link	10 Hz

5.2.8 Scoring and Ranking

Evaluation of the performance of a robot according to this functionality benchmark is based on:

1. Number and percentage of correctly grasped objects (the object stops touching the table, see definition below);
2. Execution time (if less than the maximum allowed for the benchmark).

The scoring of teams is based on the number of objects correctly grasped. A correct grasp is defined as the object being lifted from the table so to be possible for the judge to pass a hand below it. For a grasping to be “correct” the position has to be kept for at least 5 seconds from the time the judge has passes the hand below the object. The time the judge will require to verify the lifting of the object might be up to 10 seconds. In case of ties the overall execution time will be taken into account.

5.3 Manipulation Place Functionality

5.3.1 Functionality Description

This functionality benchmark assesses the robot’s capability of placing different objects inside corresponding containers. An object from a known set of possible objects is presented in the test for the robot to be placed. After grasping the object, the robot needs to perform the placing motion and place the object in a particular container/box.

5.3.2 Feature Variation

The objects used in the benchmark will be selected from the list of parts to manipulate as presented in Section 2.2. Additionally, the precise position of the object placement differs in each test.

¹⁵Pose of the grasping position on the object.

¹⁶Pose of the gripper.

¹⁷Joints data

Figure 14: Manipulation Place Functionality. Photo Credits: ERL

5.3.3 Input Provided

The team will be provided with the following information:

- The list of possible objects used in the functionality benchmark.
- Possible placement of each object used in the functionality benchmark.

5.3.4 Expected Robot Behaviour or Output

The robot is placed in front of the test area (a planar surface). One object will be placed on the robot or in its gripper. The robot now has to look the test area for any container to be placed. The robot performs the placing motion of the object and places the object in particular container in front of it. After placement it notifies the CFH.

5.3.5 Procedures and Rules

The maximum time allowed for one functionality run is 4 minutes (30 seconds for preparation and 210 seconds for execution). A run consists of (1) a preparation phase where the robot is going to its initial configuration and grasp object and (2) an execution phase in which the robot detects, localizes, recognizes and manipulates one object.

Step 1 An object of known class and known instance will be placed on the robot.

Step 2 A corresponding container for the instance is places in front of the robot.

Step 3 The robot must place the object inside the container and notify that placing has occurred.

Step 4 The preceding steps are repeated with five different objects.

5.3.6 Communication with CFH

For this functionality benchmark the robot does not have to control any networked device in the environment. Only the communication as described below is necessary:

Step 1 The robot sends a **BeaconSignal** message at least every second.

Step 2 The robot waits for a **BenchmarkState** message. It starts the preparation procedure when the *phase* field is equal to PREPARATION and the *state* field is equal to RUNNING.

Step 3 As soon as the robot finishes the preparation phase, it sends a message of type **BenchmarkFeedback** to the CFH with the *phase_to_terminate* field set to PREPARATION. The robot should do this until the **BenchmarkState**'s *phase* and *state* fields have changed.

Step 4 The robot waits for a **BenchmarkState** message. It starts the benchmark execution when the *phase* field is equal to EXECUTION and the *state* field is equal to RUNNING.

Step 5 As soon as the robot has finished manipulating the object, it sends a message of type **BenchmarkFeedback** to the CFH with the required results and the *phase_to_terminate* field set to EXECUTION. The robot should do this until the **BenchmarkState**'s *phase* and *state* fields have changed.

Step 6 The robot continues with Step 2.

Step 7 The functionality benchmark ends when the **BenchmarkState**'s *phase* field is equal to EXECUTION and the *state* field is equal to FINISHED.

The messages to be sent and to be received can be seen on the Github repository located at [2].

5.3.7 Acquisition of Benchmarking Data

General information on the acquisition of benchmarking data is described in Section 4. There, the **offline** part of the benchmarking data can be found.

Online data In order to send online benchmarking data to the CFH, the robot has to use the **BenchmarkFeedback** message. The message contains:

- *grasp_notification* (type: bool)

The **BenchmarkFeedback** message can be found at [2].

Offline data The additional information described in the following table has to be logged:

Topic	Type	Frame Id	Notes
/rockin/grasping_pose ¹⁸	geometry_msgs/PoseStamped	/base_link	10 Hz
/rockin/gripper_pose ¹⁹	geometry_msgs/PoseStamped	/base_link	10 Hz
/rockin/arm_joints ²⁰	geometry_msgs/JointState	/base_link	10 Hz

5.3.8 Scoring and Ranking

Evaluation of the performance of a robot according to this functionality benchmark is based on:

1. Number and percentage of correctly grasped objects (the object stops touching the table, see definition below);
2. Execution time (if less than the maximum allowed for the benchmark).

The scoring of teams is based on the number of objects correctly placed. A correct place is defined as the object being completely inside the container. In case of ties the overall execution time will be taken into account.

¹⁸Pose of the grasping position on the object.

¹⁹Pose of the gripper.

²⁰Joints data

6 ERL Professional ERL Professional Award Categories

6.1 Individual tournament awards

Awards will be given to the best teams for each of the Task Benchmarks (TBMs) and Functionality Benchmarks (FBMs) per tournament by the local organizers. In every Local/Major Tournament, each team is requested to perform several trials of the available TBMs and FBMs. The team score for a given TBM/FBM in a Local/Major Tournament is computed as follows:

1. Select the best five trials of the TBM/FBM by the team (all the trials if less than fiveve trial attempts are offered by the local organizers)
2. The team score is the median of the scores of the trials selected in 1.

The team with the highest score in each of the three *task benchmarks* will be awarded a certificate ("ERL Professional Best-in-class Task Benchmark <*task benchmark* title>"). When a single team participates in a given *task benchmark*, the corresponding *task benchmark* award will only be given to that team if the Executive and Technical Committees consider the team performance of exceptional level.

6.2 Best ERL Professional team award

Only one final "Best ERL Professional team" award will be awarded to the best performing team at the end of the season. The season ranking is computed as follows:

- To be eligible for an award, a team must have executed valid trials of at least one TBM in minimum two Local/Major Tournaments of the Season;
- Only TBMs are considered for computing the final score;
- A score is computed for every TBM as the median of the pooled trials used for scoring the best two performances of a team in the Local/Major Tournaments of the Season (see above);
- The team final score is then calculated by summing up all the TBM scores;
- A minimum score value will be required in order for the award to be given.

7 ERL Professional Organization

7.1 ERL Professional Infrastructure

7.1.1 ERL Professional Web Page

The official ERL Professional website can be reached at

https://eu-robotics.net/robotics_league/erl-professional/about/index.html

On this web page, teams can find introductory information about the league itself as well as relevant information about upcoming events, the most recent version of the rule book, videos and pictures of past competitions and links to further resources like the official mailing list or wiki.

7.1.2 ERL Professional Mailing List

The official ERL Professional mailing list maintained by the league is as follows

`industrial.robots_erl.rocks`

Anyone can subscribe by using the following subscription page.

https://ml06.ispgateway.de/mailman/listinfo/industrial.robots_erl.rocks

Every subscriber is requested to register either with an email address which already encodes the real name or alternatively specify it in the provided field at the subscription page. In order to prevent the mailing list from spammers, this mailing list is moderated.

The mailing list will be used for any kind of official announcement, e.g. upcoming ERL Professional competitions, rule changes, registration deadlines or infrastructure changes. Teams are welcome to raise any kind of question regarding the league on this list.

7.2 ERL Professional Competition Organization

7.2.1 Qualification and Registration

Participation in ERL Professional requires successfully passing a qualification procedure. This procedure is to ensure a well-organized competition event and the safety of participants. Depending on constraints imposed by a particular site or the number of teams interested to participate, it may not be possible to admit all interested teams to the competition.

All teams that intend to participate at the competition have to perform the following steps :

1. Preregistration – optional
2. Submission of qualification material (e.g. team description paper and video;) – mandatory
3. Final registration – mandatory, and for qualified teams only

Preregistration A team must provide the following information during the preregistration process:

- Team name + Affiliation
- Team leader name
- Team leader email address
- Expected number of team members
- Whether the team plan to bring their own robot or not
- Middleware used for software development

This step can be considered as an *Intention of Participation* declaration and serves as planning basis for the Organizing Committee.

Qualification The qualification process serves a dual purpose: It should allow the Technical Committee to assess the safety of the robots a team intends to bring to a competition, and it should allow to rank teams according to a set of evaluation criteria in order to select the most promising teams for a competition, if not all interested teams can be permitted. The TC will select the qualified teams according to the qualification material provided by the teams.

The evaluation criteria will include:

- Team description paper
- Team web site
- Relevant scientific contribution/publications
- Professional quality of robot and software
- Novelty of approach
- Relevance to industrial service robotics
- Performance in other competitions
- Contribution to ERL Professional league (e.g. by organization of events or provision and sharing of knowledge)

The Team Description Paper (TDP) is a central element of the qualification process and has to be provided by each team as part of the qualification process. The TDP should at least contain the following information in the author/title section of the paper:

- Name of the team (title)
- Team members (authors), including the team leader
- Link to the team web site
- Contact information

The body of the TDP should contain information on the following: focus of research/research interests:

- Description of the hardware, including an image of the robot(s)
- Description of the software, especially the functional and software architectures
- Main involved research areas in the team work
- Innovative technology (if any)
- Reusability of the system or parts thereof
- Applicability and relevance to industrial robotics

The team description paper should cover in detail the technical and scientific approach, while the team web site should be designed for a broader audience. Both the web site and the TDP have to be written in English.

The length of the team description paper is limited to 6 pages and has to be submitted in the IEEE Conference Proceedings format²¹.

Registration Only if a team has passed the qualification procedure successfully it is allowed to register officially for the competition and has to provide additional information e.g. the exact number of team members. Please be advised that this year, a team participating in TBM(s) for one of the Challenges (RoCKIn@Home or RoCKIn@Work) must participate in all FBMs for that Challenge. Further information about the registration procedure will be communicated through the mailing list of qualified teams. The number of people to register per team may be unlimited, but during the competition the organizers will provide space only for 6 persons to work at tables in the team area. During the final registration, each team has to designate one member as team leader. A change of the team leader must be communicated to the Organizing Committee.

²¹http://www.ieee.org/conferences_events/conferences/publishing/templates.html

7.2.2 Competition Execution

- Referees will be determined by the OC out of the group of team leaders and TC members.
- The referees ensure the correct execution of a benchmark, are in charge of keeping the time and counting the scores, being always helped by a TC or OC member.
- In case of any dangerous situation the referees are allowed to immediately stop a benchmark and trigger the emergency stop functionality of the respective robot.
- The official language for all kind of communication within the league is English (e.g., team leader meetings, announcements, schedule).
- The order in which the teams have to perform a particular benchmark will be determined by a draw through the OC.
- The order will be announced on the day before the actual benchmark.
- No team members or other persons are allowed to be in the arena during an official benchmark (only if the rule book explicitly allows/requires this).
- Regular team leader meetings (every day) will be organized and announced by the TC/OC during the competition in order to discuss open issues for upcoming benchmarks.

References

- [1] A. Ahmad, I. Awaad, F. Amigoni, J. Berghofer, R. Bischoff, A. Bonarini, R. Dwiputra, G. Fontana, F. Hegger, N. Hochgeschwender, L. Iocchi, G. Kraetzschmar, P. Lima, M. Matteucci, D. Nardi, V. Schaffionati, and S. Schneider, “Description of Ground Truth System,” Politecnico di Milano, Milan, Italy,” Deliverable D-2.1.7 (public), The RoCKIn Project (FP7-ICT-601012 grant agreement number 601012), 2014.
- [2] The RoCKIn Project. Central Factory Hub Messages. The RoCKIn Project (FP7-ICT-601012 grant agreement number 601012). [Online]. Available: https://github.com/rockin-robot-challenge/at_work_central_factory_hub/tree/rockin/rockin/messages